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TU Delft's First Genomics Data Carpentry

Raúl teaching the participants about data wrangling and processing on the second day.

On the 4th and 5th of June 2019, a [Genomics Data Carpentry](#) took place at TU Delft for Early Career Researchers at the Faculties of Applied Sciences and Electrical Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science. This workshop was organised by the [Data Champions](#) [Raúl A. Ortiz Merino](#) and [Marcel van den Broek](#), with the support of the Data Stewards and [Paula Martinez Lavanchy](#) from [4TU.ResearchData](#). Helpers were [Mario Beck](#), [Kees den Heijer](#), [Nicolas Dintzner](#) and [Barbara Vreede](#) (Utrecht University).

Participants gave feedback using blue post-its to indicate what could be improved and yellow post-its to let us know what they liked about the Data Carpentry.

The 21 participants used their own laptops and learned about [project organization for genomics](#) from Esther, [cloud genomics](#) from Santosh, and [shell for genomics](#) and [data wrangling and processing](#) by both Raúl and Marcel (see also the programme of the workshop on [GitHub](#)). No prior knowledge of the tools that were used during the workshop was required. Collaborative notes were taken using [Etherpad](#). PhD's were able to get credits for following the course.

Future Carpentry Workshops

The next software carpentry will take place on the 8-9th of July. The Data Stewards can also be contacted to organise smaller sessions to support beginners with their code/software, or you can join one of our **Coding Lunch and Data Crunch** walk in consultation sessions where we can also support you with more advanced problems. The next one is on the 27th of June (12:00 – 14:00, IDE, Studio 23/24).